

Guide

Montag, 6. März 2023 10:43

Privacy Information

- Interview will be recorded
- Recording will be deleted immediately after notes were approved by interviewee
- Notes will be pseudonymized
- No publication of notes
- Mentions of notes and pseudonymized name of interviewee in paper

Demographics

- Current role
- Years of professional experience in ML/MLOps

General

Please answer the following questions based on your personal professional experience.

- What general components should most ML pipelines have? (if participant has problems to name components, show frequently used ones compiled from literature)
- What situational components do some ML pipelines have? (if participant has problems to name components, show frequently used ones compiled from literature)
- What are the most important quality requirements for ML pipelines? (if participant has problems to name requirements, show frequently used ones compiled from literature)
- What are the most common challenges regarding ML pipelines? (if participant has problems to name requirements, show frequently used ones compiled from literature)
- How do components and quality requirements of an ML pipeline depend on ...
 - the dataset?
 - the industry domain?
 - the team expertise?
 - the type of ML, e.g., supervised, unsupervised, reinforcement learning, etc.?
 - the type of problem, e.g., regression, classification, forecasting, action learning, etc.?
 - other factors?

Frequent components:

- Feature Store
- Model Registry
- Experiment Tracker

Situational components:

- Data Visualization
- Parallel Training

Important quality requirements:

- Quality Assurance
- Explainability

Common challenges:

- Data quality
- Automation
- Monitoring
- Versioning

Projects

- What kind of ML project are you currently working on?
 - Industry domain
 - Type of problem
 - Requirements
 - Goals
- ML pipeline
 - Basic description
 - Quality requirements
 - Special components
 - Encountered challenges
 - during start of project
 - during development
 - during release phases

Pipeline Generation

- What challenges could be addressed by automatically generating full ML pipelines (or some pipeline components)?
- What ML pipeline components do you see as prime candidates to be automatically generated?
 - Potential to reduce time?
 - Potential to reduce mistakes?
- Would you trust an automatically generated component? Why? Why not?
- What configuration input would you see as important for an ML pipeline generation approach?
 - What attributes?
 - How (JSON/YAML/GUI/questions)?

Use Case Example:

- Classification of flowers
- Wanted features
 - Versioning of data, code and model
 - Monitoring of performance metrics

Results

Donnerstag, 16. März 2023 10:19

Time: between 70-80 minutes

Demographics

- All 5 interviewees are data scientists
- Between 3-4.5 years of professional experience in ML
- P2 only one year in MLOps
- P4 only 1.5 to 2 years
- P5 6-7 years

General

Components:

- Requirements Engineering (P4)
 - o What is the goal of the customer?
 - o How does the current process look like?
- Data Engineering Pipeline
 - o Participants
 - For P1 not as important/talked less about it than P2 and P3
 - P3 a lot of details on data engineering
 - o Parts
 - Data acquisition
 - Data ingestion/loading
 - Database/On-demand
 - CSV
 - Data analysis
 - Data visualization (P4)
 - ◆ Data distribution
 - ◆ Feature importance
 - ◆ Correlation between features
 - Data Preparation
 - Data Cleansing
 - Combining and transforming data
 - Handling outliers
 - Enriching data
 - Feature Engineering
- (Train-test split)
 - o Mentioned by P2 (in "Project" section) and P3 (in "General" section)
- Model Training
 - o Grid-Search
 - o Hyperparameter Tuning
 - o Model Registry
 - o Experiment Tracker
- Model Testing/Validation
 - o Report of model quality/accuracy
 - o Metrics depend on kind of problem and data (P4)
 - Example: Classification with 98% of data with one label, model is 98% of the time correct by always predicting this label
- Model deployment
 - o Prediction pipeline (prepares and validates data for model usage)
 - o Preprocessing + Model
 - o How?
 - As service via API endpoint
 - As batch job
 - As artifact (Statically embedded) (P2)
- Monitoring
 - o Monitoring pipeline
 - o Components independent from ML pipeline
 - o Monitor data & feature, looking for drift (P1,2,3)
 - o Prediction and its distribution, Fairness and bias (P3)
 - o Performance metrics of the model (P4)
 - o Does model need retraining? (P2)
- Retraining (P1, P2, P3, P5)

Quality requirements:

Functional:

- **Monitoring**
 - o Model scoring depending on what is time tested (P1)
 - o Which metrics are important for use case? (P4)
- **Data quality assurance** (P2, P4)
 - o Data quality and format are guaranteed
 - o Manually in proof-of-concept (P4)
 - o Automatically in latter stages (P4)

Non-functional:

- **Testability** (P3)
 - o Automated
 - o Single components (unit-tests)
 - o Interoperability of steps (integration tests)
- **Flexibility**
 - o Kedro: easy change of dataset
- **Structure/Modularity**
 - o Folder structure (P2)
 - o Extracted hyperparameters (in config file) (P3)
 - o Modularity (P5)
- Pipeline performance (duration of run, parallelization) (P3)
- Good documentation & clean code (P5)
- Reusability (P3)

P1 components

- Pipeline for training
- Pipeline in production
 - o Preprocessing + Model
 - o Batch process
 - o API endpoint
- Scoring batches
- Dependent on customers tech stack
 - o Custom frameworks

Where does Data Pipeline end and ML pipeline start?
Idea: Feature Engineering first part of ML pipeline

Mentioned technology:

- Kedro
- Hadoop cluster
- PySpark
- Databricks
- Mlflow

Mentioned libraries:

- Pandas
- Tensorflow
- LGBM

Graphical tools: Generic code not suitable for more complex use cases/data

Pipeline visualization: barely mentioned, deemed as essential/standard

Monitoring independent from ML pipeline (P1)

Kedro & MLflow for initialization of pipeline

Challenges

- **No standard procedure for setting up a pipeline** (P1, P3)
 - With retraining and monitoring (P1)
 - Creating the pipeline from scratch (P1)
 - Building ml pipeline from proof-of-concept jupyter notebook (P3)
 - Because Review difficult
 - Because other developers can't get any value out of these notebooks
- **Data quality** (P2, P4)
 - Missing values
 - Data visualization
 - Unlabelled data (P4)
- Results (of predictions) don't match with expected results (by domain experts) (P4)
- **Configuration** (P5)
 - Configuring own docker containers
- Model and code **testing** (P5)
- **Deployment** (P5)
 - Kind of deployment
 - e.g., Batch processing
 - Non-automatic deployment (P1)
 - Depends on deployment by customer
- P3: Dependent on many questions (Necessary features, number of runs, ...)

Aggregation = Preprocessing

Dependencies

- From dataset
 - Data quality (P1)
 - Data preprocessing depend on data quality (P2)
 - Data visualization and data quality profile helpful (distribution, missing values) (P2)
 - Heterogeneity and homogeneity (P3)
 - Complexity (P3)
 - In contact with domain experts (P3)
 - Data aggregation (P3)
 - Missing values (P3, P5)
 - Duplicates (P5)
 - Bigger data pipeline depending on data quality (P4)
 - Data quantity (P1, P3)
 - Is extending the data an option? (P3)
 - Data format (P1)
 - Different data formats (P3)
 - Data sources (P3)
 - Different sources/different systems as sources (P3)
 - Data acquisition (P3)
 - Monitoring (P5)
 - Looking for data drift
 - Data security
 - Data is stored in customers infrastructure/cloud
 - Restricted access to data
 - Anonymization
- From industry domain
 - Special requirements in terms of tech stack (P1)
 - Missing infrastructure (P1)
 - More regulations in closely regulated companies and institutions (bank, insurances, etc.) (P2)
 - Good data quality
 - Documented data origin
 - Traceability
 - Little to no influence, use case more important (P3, P4, P5)
- From team expertise
 - Software engineers more focused on implementation compared to scientific personnel (P1)
 - Also dependencies on available toolset (P1)
 - Experimenting/Prototyping: every ML practitioner for him-/herself (P2)
 - MLOps: Validating, testing (P2)
 - Expectations by domain experts (later in comparison with model) (P3, P4)
 - Faster progress (based on more experience with data and feature engineering) (P4)
 - Work as team is influenced by different skill sets, less the pipeline (P5)
- From type of ML (supervised, ...)
 - Supervised
 - No batch jobs, API endpoints (P1)
 - Unsupervised
 - Batch jobs, on-demand (P1)
 - needs manual validation/more used for analysis (P5)
 - Different metrics (P3)
 - Little influence (P3)
- Type of problem (regression, classification, ...)
 - Clustering feedback loop doesn't need to be that short compared to recommendation system (P1)
 - No/little influence (P2, P3, P4, P5)
 - Different metrics for model validation (P4, P5)
- Other factors
 - No other factors (P2)
 - Response time/Model execution speed (P1, P3)
 - Availability (e.g., specific time) (P1)
 - Data preprocessing execution speed (P3)
 - Testing the service with expected load (P3)
 - Functional requirements: Model performance (accuracy) (P3)
 - Resources/computational power (P4)

Project

- Use cases
 - Telecommunication company (P1)
 - Recommendation system
 - Call campaigns
 - Mail campaigns
 - Pipeline:
 - Data warehouse
 - Scoring using custom framework (committed by customer)
 - Monitoring using dashboards filled on a daily basis
 - Challenges:
 - Custom framework (new and bad documented)
 - Non-automatic model deployment
 - Investment and development bank (P2)

- Prediction of money needed for providing loans and subsidies
- Pipeline:
 - Data preparation
 - ◆ Import, merge, inspection, train-test-split, prevent data leakage, feature engineering
 - Modelling
 - ◆ Grid search (model algorithms and hyperparameters)
 - Validation
- Challenges:
 - Start: Data acquisition and understanding
 - Development: Requirements and non-specialist colleagues not having knowledge about ML
- Investment and development bank (P3)
 - Automation of subsidy allowance
 - No ML, only data and using external AI service (Azure cognitive services)
 - Pipeline (no ML, just data)
 - Challenges
 - ◆ Data heterogeneous
 - ◆ Many different data sources
 - ◆ Problem with data leakage
- Multiple older projects (P4)
 - Automobile association
 - Predict call center load (number of expected calls resulting in prediction for number of needed staff)
 - Problem: time series forecasting
 - Sports startup
 - Controlling camera movement and zoom based on live images and what viewers want to see
 - Goal: replace sports cinematographer
 - Problem: object recognition
 - Special case: sport in halls/sport centers
 - Better image quality because of external influences (e.g. weather)
 - Steel company
 - Prediction of materials the steel consists of
 - Problem: regression
 - Data (format) can't even be explained by customer (customer doesn't know what some parts of data mean)
- Sports recognition model (P5)
 - Computer vision problem, detection of person, ball, phases of a jump, etc.
 - Open source models
 - No pipeline yet

Pipeline Generation

- Addressed challenges
 - Generator as bridge between prototyping/experimentation and getting that code into a pipeline (P1)
 - Hyperparameter not somewhere in code (P3)
 - Easier first initialization of pipeline (P3)
 - Time saving (P4)
 - Reduction of mistakes (P4)
- Prime candidates
 - When a model already exists: everything after model engineering (P1)
 - Abstract parts (P1)
 - For monitoring:
 - feature type and range as input (P1)
 - Simple metrics for performance scoring (P1)
 - Requested features
 - Versioning (P2, P5)
 - Data (P5)
 - Model Validation (P2, P5)
 - Generating report (P2)
 - Backlogging (P5)
 - Gateway with metrics (P5)
 - Model Registry (P2, P5 as part of Versioning)
 - Data pipeline in production (P2)
 - Grid-search for model algorithm and hyperparameters (P3, hint P4)
 - Metric for performance
 - Data visualization using PowerBI/Tableau/qlik(P3, hint P4)
 - Pipeline as data source of PowerBI/... (P3)
 - Feature Importance (P4)
 - Automatic exclusion of unimportant features
 - Correlation analysis (P4)
 - For feature exclusion
 - Automatic feature generation based on important features (P4)
 - Explainability of AI (P4)
 - Possible feature: Extending pipeline automatically (Existing pipeline as input -> gets extended by one feature) (P1)
 - Hyperparameter extracted in files (P3)
 - Modularity of pipeline and files/folder structure
- Trust?
 - After some time
 - When the tool proved to be reliable
- Configuration input
 - Model training
 - Problem type (P1, P2)
 - Model type (P1, P2) / Selection of models (P4)
 - Selection of features (P4)
 - Type of model features (P1)
 - Orientation towards AutoML (P2)
 - Parameter ranges for each model (P2)
 - Metrics for scoring the model (P2)
 - Classification: threshold for choosing one class
 - Monitoring (P1, P2)
 - Selection of features (P1)
 - Selection of performance metrics (P1)
 - Predefined feature stores (P1)
 - Previously created features from others projects (P1)
 - Deployment
 - Deployment type (API endpoint, stream processing, batch processing?) (P1)
 - Deployment kind (A/B tests, ...) (P2)

Difference to ...

- Kedro
 - Features of kedro
 - Versioning (data, model)
 - configuration
 - Pipelines can be extended (hooks)
 - Project structure is generated
 - Manually created functions as pipeline steps
 - Missing features/problems with kedro
 - Initialized project complex
 - Data integration (practically always manual work because of different kind of data systems)
- Platforms of cloud providers (Vertex AI, Azure ML, ...)
- Building pipeline with drag & drop
- A lot of features already provided
- AutoML
 - Automatic data and model engineering
 - Here: everything around this

Generator

Freitag, 31. März 2023 10:55

Components

- Data pipeline
 - o Data Ingestion
 - o Dataset Join
 - o Data Versioning
 - o Data Visualization
 - Data Distribution
 - Outliers
 - Missing values
 - Feature correlation
- Model Pipeline
 - o Train-test split
 - Cross validation?
 - Train-test ratio (how many data points does each consist of?)
 - o Model training
 - Grid search? (/AutoML)
 - Model algorithms + hyperparameter ranges
 - Model Registry
 - Experiment Tracker
 - o Model validation
 - Metrics depend on input
 - Report on accuracy
- Deployment Pipeline
 - o Preprocessing steps + Model
 - o Where?
 - o How?
 - A/B tests
 - Blue-green deployment
 - ...
 - o As?
 - API endpoint
 - Batch
- Model Monitoring
 - o Data, Feature & Prediction (Distribution, fairness, bias)
 - o Retraining (trigger)

Data Ingestion: already automated by kedro (data catalog)

Configuration-dependent
Configuration-independent

Feature importance?

Parallel training?

User Input: (How?)

- CLI walk-through
- Config file
- GUI

Guide

Montag, 6. März 2023 09:32

Experience with Kedro and Mlflow

- **Experience with Kedro:** Years of professional experience
- **Experience with MLflow:** Years of professional experience

If the participant has no experience with kedro, the interviewer will explain the folder and file structure as well as kedro-viz.
If the participant has no experience with MLflow, the interviewer will explain the basic functionality using the MLflow UI.

Pull Generator

Clone repo

Switch to branch 'mlpipegen'

Create example project

Create venv (python -m venv)

Import packages from requirements.txt

Copy example datasets from the generator repo to example_project/data/01_raw

Exercise

- Play around for 10 minutes
- Exercise: think aloud for 20 minutes
 - o Classification task with diabetes prediction dataset
 - o 2 datasets: diabetes prediction dataset and smoking history dataset
 - o Goal: Build a pipeline with min-max scaling and outlier removal
 - Pipeline can run successfully
 - Participant can view documentation + ask questions about doc and input
 - Interviewer can give tips if stuck

Quantitative Questions: Survey

Questions about Usefulness gehen über den Ansatz, Ease of Use über Prototypen !!!

Qualitative Questions

- **General:** How can the generator be improved? How should the generator work differently than it does now?
- **Interaction:**
 - o User input
 - How can the user input be improved?
 - What kind of user input/user interaction would you prefer?
 - o Program execution
 - How would you like to start the generation process?
 - What output format/kind do you prefer? (Current: Existing kedro project is modified)
- **Resulting pipeline:**
 - o Pipeline structure
 - What do you think about the structure of the resulting pipeline?
 - How would you improve the structure of the resulting pipeline?
 - o Support for data engineering algorithms
 - How can the existing data engineering algorithms can be improved?
 - What data engineering algorithms would you want to be added?
 - o Support for feature engineering algorithms
 - How can the existing feature engineering algorithms can be improved?
 - What feature engineering algorithms would you want to be added?
 - o More general AutoML
 - What do you think about AutoML as part of the resulting pipeline?
 - Would you use an AutoML functionality?
 - o Model Deployment Pipeline
 - How important would be a generated model deployment pipeline for you?
 - What functionality could be part of a model deployment pipeline?
 - o Tool & platform support besides kedro & MLflow
 - Which platforms would you like being supported?
 - Which tools would you like being supported?

Results

Dienstag, 6. Juni 2023 08:14

Duration: around 55-70 minutes

Experience with Kedro & Mlflow:

- Kedro: P2 one year, P3 used a while ago, others none
- Mlflow: P1 has some experience, P2 used it once, P3 one year, others none

- Simple template.yml already present (classification task with both datasets listed, only FE needed to be added for exercise)
- Problems with ...
 - program execution:
 - o flags (-f, -l), project location, prototype location, paths (P5, P2)
 - Frequency of switching between project and prototype (P4)
 - Feature engineering configuration
 - o Listing all features, no exclusion of features (all participants)
 - Diabetes (target label) was **always** added to feature list
 - o Copy&paste of features from csv
 - o Target label already existed in the config file
 - Yaml syntax: especially the FE part where every feature is a separate dictionary (P1, P2)
 - o Typo was ignored -> no error (P4)
- Good:
 - Easy creation of input file (P1)
 - Easy entry for pipeline creation (P1)
 - Straight-forward for creating an ML pipeline (P5)
 - Good for standardizing ML pipelines & code across multiple projects (P1)
 - Good for project start, creating first models (P4, P5)
 - First results in a few minutes (P5)
 - Ease of use (only few commands) (P3)
 - Currently: good for local development with small datasets (P1)
 - o Too simplistic for low quality datasets
 - Ease of learning:
 - o Participants are able to recall the usage of the prototype during the exercise
 - Code & structure seem correct
 - o Scaling test and training data with same scaler separately (P2)
 - Data visualization (P5)
 - o Related to Dataiku (P1)
 - o Helpful (for "testing" manually programmed preprocessing steps) (P1)
 - o Alternative (hook executing jupyter notebook) (P2, P3)
 - o Pandas profiling (P2)
 - Mlflow tracking (plots etc) (P3)
- Questions about ...
 - Joining of dataset (different algorithms, timeframes, ...) (P1)
 - Multiclass classification (P1)
 - Default values of preprocessing unclear (P1)
 - Focus on big data and distributed computation (P1)
 - Whether prototype can be moved into the kedro project (P2)
 - No output good or bad? (P2)
 - How to use -> documentation insufficient (P3, P4)
- Behavior
 - Participant looks at generated code instead of pipeline visualization (P2)
 - Looks at prototype code (P3)
 - Participant expects to find step "joining datasets" in config file

Generally, more time needed with prototype to evaluate functionalities, how useful it is (in its current state) and what can be improved

Execution of pipeline takes long (P3, P4)

Improvements:

- Joining datasets often more complex (P2)
- Complex use cases? Good for simple ones (P5)
- Feature selection and preprocessing (all participants)
- More preprocessing algorithms
 - o Really complex topic for automatic generation, AI? (P2)
 - o Too many possible algorithms, depending on data, needs to be extracted from experimentation (P3)
 - o Handling missing values (P4)
 - o Feature generation (P4)
- Better documentation
 - o Participant is not aware of the generated kedro parameters -> no more generation needed for changing those (P2)
- Generator be part of kedro (for easier handling) (P2)
 - o Switching between prototype and kedro project: prototype inside kedro (as plugin or some sort?) (All participants)
- Support for other problems and datasets (e.g. images, text, video,...) (P5)
- Output of pipeline can be (sklearn) pipeline (production pipeline) (P1)
- Structure of pipeline:
 - o Most participants thought it was good
 - o P3 expects scaling to be part of data pipeline (-> does data leakage mistake)
- Input:
 - o Config file good (P2, P4, P3)
 - Clear and understandable with good documentation
 - Might have boundaries when it comes to complex use cases
 - o UI (P1, P5, P3)
 - Web app for changing configurations (P3)
 - AI recommends changes to pipeline (P3)
- AutoML:
 - o Grid search can be replaced with more general AutoML (all participants)
 - o Grid search and AutoML can be used together (P3)
- Deployment pipeline necessary but many options possible
 - o Difficult
 - o Docker as standard, docker image configurations could be collected during pipeline run (P3)

P1: Prototype similar to framework used in project (customer framework)

- Defined operators for preprocessing
- Production MLOps pipeline
- Definition via yaml file
- Prototype more for model training/retraining

- Not necessarily important for initial testing (P4)
- Configurations mentioned: definition of environment variables, runtimes, scripts, models, inferencing, inference speed, availability, scaling,... (P5)
- Support for other libraries (outside of scikit-learn) (P2)
- Distributed computation (P1)
- Platform & tool support:
 - Different requirements for projects depending on amount of data and existing infrastructure (P1)
 - Kedro & Mlflow good enough (P2)
 - Tools for deployment (P3)
 - Azure (P4)
 - Cloud providers in general (P5)
- Ideas:
 - Kedro as underlying framework -> ML practitioner only needs to work with prototype (P3)
 - Extension of existing pipelines (maybe by adding code snippets, e.g. code inserts like Git) (P2)